

Number Zero property in factoring a number into prime factors (Addition of Zeros)

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Abstract

This property of prime numbers is based on the addition of a number of zeros between a prime number (P) and the same prime number (P) to form a compound number usually always, except in rare cases, from three prime factors where two factors are always the prime number 11, the first number (P) and a third prime number which is always 9090..9091 (ends with the number 91 but the initial number 90 repeats but depends on the size of prime number (P). The amount of Zeros to be added is equal to the number of digits of the prime number (P) . If I take the prime number 43 for the assumption which has two digits have to add three zeros and the number becomes 4300043 .

$$(P) + \text{Zero} + (P)$$

Content

I demonstrate with two examples that the number obtained from the formula (P) + Zeros + (P) , you have to divide with the number 11 and with the number (P) to get the first factor 90.....9091 .

Example 1

No. 43

%1 = 43
? 4300043
%2 = 4300043
? %2/11
%3 = 390913
? %3/%1
%4 = 9091

Example 2

No.

**19008712816648221131268515739354139754718967899685154936666385390880271038021
04498957191261465571**

